

ISic0421

I.Sicily inscription 0421

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Roma

Place of origin (modern)

Rome

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [D(is)] · M(anibus)
2. [---]aeli · Euty chionis
3. [---]ius · Aelius · Euty chio · et
4. [---]Aelia Gemella · parentes
5. [filiod]ulcissimo · fecerunt · qui
6. [vix(it) an]n(is) · VIII · mens(ibus) · IIII · dieb(us) · XXVII

Apparatus

Text of CIL

CIL tentatively restores "Aureli?" at start

CIL tentatively restores "Aurel?" at start

CIL restores "Aurelia" at start

Translation

Commentary

CIL X.2, add., p.993 states: 'Dele; venit ex urbe (n.1068*, n.9a). Correct to 1088*.9a

Digital identifiers:

TM 575350

EDCS 21900542

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7141 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650768>)

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0421. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4335606>